

OPTIMISING
ENERGY USE IN
CITIES THROUGH
SMART DECISION
SUPPORT SYSTEMS

FP7/608703

Published data in an open data portal

Deliverable number D3.1

This document has been prepared within the framework of the European project “OPTIMising the energy USE in cities with smart decision support system (OPTIMUS)” co-financed by the European Commission through the “Seventh Framework (FP7)” Programme (Grant agreement no 608703).

Start date of the project: October 2013

End date of the project: October 2016

Deliverable no: 3.1

Deliverable title: Published data in an open data portal

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1 Introduction

This deliverable summarises the outcomes of Task 3.1 *Semantic Framework For Data Integration* as part of Work Package 3 *Semantic Data Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS*. The purpose of this task is to implement methods and tools to provide an integrated access to the data captured and modelled in WP2 using semantic technologies. This implies transforming the raw data captures with the different modules (see Deliverables 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6) into meaningful information to end-users. The methods and tools developed in this task are based on the architecture proposed in Deliverable 2.1 *Overall Architecture of OPTIMUS DSS*. They provide an integrated access to real-time data from multiple sources captured and modelled using semantic technologies.

The interoperability between the DSS and the data provided by the modules created in WP2, is achieved through a semantic framework based on Semantic Web technologies that enables to capture and model the data sources using a global ontology schema.

The outcomes of this task have been the following:

- A semantic integration process to capture and model data sources from different domains (i.e. weather data, building energy systems, social media, energy prices, and energy production data).
- An ontology –i.e. the OPTIMUS ontology– which stands for a shared conceptualization of the urban and building domains including monitoring devices formally implemented as an OWL ontology. The OPTIMUS ontology extends and reuses already existing ontologies (i.e. SEMANCO ontology and Semantic Sensor Network ontologies).
- A Semantic framework which is composed of a set of RDF templates used by the data capturing modules for modelling real-time data according to the OPTIMUS ontology; a pub/sub system acting as a communication system between the data capturing modules and the DSS implemented with Ztreamy system, and a semantic service which processes the data in a specific context.

2 Semantic data integration process

The OPTIMUS DSS relies on the interconnection of five heterogeneous real-time data sources which are used to suggest short-term actions plans for public authorities with the goal of reducing energy consumption in public buildings. Typically, these data are generated by different sources such as physical sensors installed in buildings (e.g. energy consumption), national agencies (e.g. weather forecast, energy prices) and web services (e.g. social media networks). Moreover, the data belongs to different realms (e.g. climate, energy costs) and have different characteristics (e.g. units of measure, aggregation level, data encoding). For integrating these heterogeneous data, it is necessary a holistic interoperability solution such as the one provided by semantic web technologies.

The Semantic Web approach postulated by Tim Berners-Lee is a widely adopted solution to integrate heterogeneous data sources from different realms. In particular, it has been increasingly adopted by local administrations and governments thanks to the impulse given by the open data movements (Lopez et al. 2012). The Semantic Web community and, in

particular, the Linked Data movement, promotes the use of ontologies to connect heterogeneous sources of data handled by different domain experts.

As defined by Gruber (1993) an ontology is “an explicit specification of a conceptualization” where “conceptualization” is a simplified view of the world that is modelled for a particular purpose, thus the knowledge that one might wish to model should be explicitly specified by means of concepts and relations formally coded in a particular language such as Ontology Web Language (OWL). The interoperability issues raised when between data from different domains and sources is integrated. This can be solved through the creation of an ontology which encapsulates the specific properties of data sources with the final purpose of having the data modelled according to a shared conceptualization. In this way, the data is encoded in Resource Description Language (RDF) enabling to describe Web resources under a common and a general-purpose language designed to be read and understood by computers. Semantic information can be formalized in RDF graphs as a set of RDF triples —subject-predicate-object statements—, to show facts and relations which are represented by an ontology. Through a data link level defined in RDF graphs, it is possible to create a network of linked data, available for any application.

A data integration process has been devised in this project to fulfil the requirements and particularities of the OPTIMUS Decision Support System architecture defined in D2.1 *Overall Architecture of OPTIMUS DSS*:

- Data capturing module communication with the DSS based on a publish-and-subscribe system.
- Semantic representation of the data based on existing ontologies, vocabularies and ISO/CEN standards.
- Easy deployment and reconfiguration of the different components of the DSS.

The data integration process is based on Semantic Web technologies and it encompasses four steps (Figure 1):

- 1) Data translation,
- 2) Data communication,
- 3) Data contextualization, and
- 4) Data storage

Since an ontology is used for producing the RDF data and for giving context, the data integration is guaranteed.

Figure 1. Semantic data integration process

2.1 Step 1: Data translation.

The data capturing modules (see Deliverables 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6) translate the data from the original format into RDF according to a global ontology, namely the OPTIMUS ontology. The data is modelled using triples with “subject – predicate – object” expressions which reflect the structure of the OPTIMUS ontology. For example, the energy production data capturing module will generate the following triples (Figure 2) for modelling the solar radiation data measured by a sensor in the Sant Cugat pilot.

```

<uri/observation/sunnyportal_solar_radiation1> ssn:observedBy <uri/sensingdevice/sunnyportal_solar_radiation>.
<uri/observation/sunnyportal_solar_radiation1> ssn:observationResult <uri/sensoroutput/sunnyportal_solar_radiation1>.
<uri/observation/sunnyportal_solar_radiation1> ssn:observationResultTime <uri/instant/201509260510>.
<uri/sensoroutput/sunnyportal_solar_radiation1> ssn:hasValue "12345"^^xsd:decimal.
<uri/instant/201509260510> time:inXSDdateTime "2014-09-26T05:10:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime.
  
```

Figure 2. Examples of RDF data sent by the Energy production data capturing module

Some parts of the triples depend on the measured data (red coloured ones in Figure 2), that is, on the value measured and when it was measured. Other parts of the triples (green coloured ones), depend on the sensor that is measuring the data. Finally, there are internal identifiers (blue-coloured) which are needed for keeping the consistency of the data. All of the other components of the triples are “static”.

In order to model the monitored data as RDF, the data capturing modules fill a template by instantiating a set of variables (Figure 3). The idea is that some of the variables could be externally configured (e.g. the variables in bold: city name, sensor name) while other variables may be generated on-the-fly (e.g. *timeid*, *id*, *value*). In this way, it is easy to deploy the capturing modules in different scenarios. The triples follows the OPTIMUS ontology which is described in detailed in section 3 of this document.

```

#Global variables
{city}: city_name (e.g. sant_cugat)
{resource_uri}: www.optimus-smartcity.eu/resources/{pilot} (e.g. www.optimus-smartcity.eu/resources/{city})
#Variables with regard a particular sensor
{sensor}: sensor_name (e.g. sunnyportal_solar_radiation)
#Variables with regard a "data point" of a sensor (in SSN a data point is called observation)
{timeid}: {year}{month}{day}{hour}{miute}{second}{millisecond} (e.g. 201409251739000)
{time_in_xsd}: {year}-{month}-{day}T{hour}:{miute}:{second}Z (e.g. 2014-09-25T05:10:00:00Z)
{value}: numeric value of the monitored data (e.g. 23)
{id}: unique ID by event data (e.g. 123456)

<{resource_uri}/observation/{sensor}{id}> ssn:observedBy <{resource_uri}/sensingdevice/{sensor}>.
<{resource_uri}/observation/{sensor}{id}> ssn:observationResult <{resource_uri}/sensoroutput/{sensor}{id}>.
<{resource_uri}/observation/{sensor}{id}> ssn:observationResultTime <{resource_uri}/instant/{timeid}>.
<{resource_uri}/sensoroutput/{sensor}{id}> ssn:hasValue "{value}"^^xsd:decimal.
<{resource_uri}/instant/{timeid}> time:inXSDdateTime "{time_in_xsd}"^^xsd:dateTime.

```

Figure 3. Variables and the template for generating RDF triples

2.2 Step 2: Data communication.

The RDF data is sent to the DSS using a publish-and-subscribe system (i.e. Ztreamy server). Each data capturing module publishes their data using a set of channels/streams, one stream per each sensor which provides a specific physical quantity or type of information. A data capturing module can have more than one sensor and a sensor can monitor more than one physical phenomenon. Every monitored data is sent by a single stream. Figure 4 shows some examples of the interrelationships of data capturing modules, sensors and measured data.

Figure 4. Examples of interrelationships of data capturing modules, sensors, and measured data.

The streams are identified with a name which should be known by the server, the publishers (i.e. data capturing modules) and the subscribers (i.e. DSS). The pattern used to name the streams is the following:

<city>_<pilot>_<module>_<sensor>_<type of data>

For example, a stream for the energy production data capturing module would be as follows:

santcugat_townhall_energyproduction_pvplant_power

If a data capturing module covers more than one building, such as energy prices or weather forecast, the stream names would be:

spanish_energyprices_energycost

spanish__weatherforecast_outdoor_airtemperature

2.3 Step 3: Data contextualization.

The Semantic Service receives the RDF triples from the publish-and-subscribe system and processes them. The context is represented by a set of triples which describe the static features of the sensor which sends data. Figure 5 shows an example of the RDF triples that are needed to contextualize the data, such as the property measured by the sensor.

```

<{uri}/observation/sunnyportal_solar_radiation(id)> ssn:featureOfInterest <{uri}/featureofinterest/solar_irradiation>.
<{uri}/observation/sunnyportal_solar_radiation(id)> ssn:observedProperty <{uri}/property/solar_radiation>.
<{uri}/sensoroutput/sunnyportal_solar_radiation(id)> rdf:type optimus:Solar_IrradiationSensorOutput.

<{uri}/sensingdevice/sunnyportal_solar_radiation> rdf:type optimus:SunnyPortal_SolarRadiation.
<{uri}/featureofinterest/solar_irradiation> rdf:type optimus:Solar_IrradiationFeature.
<{uri}/featureofinterest/solar_irradiation> ssn:hasProperty <{uri}/property/solar_radiation>.

```

Figure 5. RDF triples used the Semantic Service to enhance the Energy Production data following the example of Figure 2

2.4 Step 4: Data storage.

The Semantic Service uploads the final RDF triples on a triple store (e.g. Virtuoso server). The DSS components, such as the front-end interfaces and the DSS engine, access the triple store by means of RDF queries written in SPARQL Query Language. Figure 6 shows an example of a SPARQL query to retrieve RDF data generated by the renewable energy production data capturing module.

```

PREFIX time: <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
PREFIX ssn: <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#>

SELECT DISTINCT ?power ?radiation ?datetime
WHERE {
?obs1 ssn:observedBy <../sant_cugat/sensingdevice/sunnyportal_energy_production>;
      ssn:observationResult [ssn:hasValue ?power];
      ssn:observationResultTime [time:inXSDDateTime ?datetime].

?obs2 ssn:observedBy <../sant_cugat/sensingdevice/sunnyportal_solar_radiation>;
      ssn:observationResult [ssn:hasValue ?radiation];
      ssn:observationResultTime [time:inXSDDateTime ?datetime].
} ORDER BY ?datetime

```

Figure 6. SPARQL query to retrieve data

The query asks for power and solar radiation measured by the sensors *sunnyportal_energy_production* and *sunnyportal_solar_radiation*. The output list is ordered according to date and time.

3 The OPTIMUS ontology

The OPTIMUS ontology is a formal shared conceptualization of a building in operation, created with the purpose of improving its energy efficiency. It contains the terms and attributes to describe regions, cities, neighbourhoods, buildings, building partitions, systems and metering devices, indicators such as energy consumption and CO₂ emission, as well as climate and socio-economic factors. The purpose of defining this ontology is twofold:

- To reach consensus about the meaning of terms such as the elements of buildings (zone, area, sector, floor...), units (Celsius, kWh...) and how they relate to each other.
- To integrate the diverse data sources using the terminology agreed.

3.1 Ontology structure

The ontology models the static (e.g. building and technical systems features) and the dynamic (e.g. metering) characteristics of a building and their context (e.g. climate conditions and energy costs). In the field of ontology engineering, it is considered to be a good practice reusing existing ontologies or vocabularies to avoid reinventing the wheel and to increase the interoperability of the ontology. The OPTIMUS ontology is based on two already existing ontologies: Urban Energy ontology¹ and Semantic Sensor Network ontology² (Figure 7).

Figure 7. OPTIMUS ontology modules

With respect to the static data, the Urban Energy ontology has been extended to model the building and technical system features collected in Deliverable 2.1 such as building geometry, building thermal envelope, DHW systems, space cooling/heating systems, and energy generator. The concepts and properties not included in this ontology have been created in a new ontology called OPTIMUS. The Urban Energy ontology was chosen because it conceptualizes the same domain as the OPTIMUS ontology and it is based on existing energy information standards, including: the ISO/IEC CD 13273 Energy efficiency regulation and renewable energy sources, the ISO/DTR 16344 Common terms, the definitions and symbols for the overall energy performance rating and certification of buildings, the ISO/CD 16346 Assessment of overall energy performance of buildings, the ISO/DIS 12655 Presentation of real energy use of buildings, the ISO/CD 16343 Methods for expressing energy performance

¹ <http://semanco-tools.eu/urban-energy-ontology>

² <http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/ssnx/ssn>

and for energy certification of buildings, and the ISO 50001:2011 Energy management systems – requirements with guidance for use (Nemirovski et al. 2013).

Concerning the dynamic data, the Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology has been extended to include all the metering systems available in the pilot cities. The SSN ontology can describe sensors and observations. In particular, this ontology includes capabilities, measurement processes, observations and deployments in which sensors are used (Compton et al. 2012). The ontology is aligned with an upper ontology (i.e. Dolce Ultra Light ontology³) and it is compatible with SensorML and O&M (Observations and Measurements) standards of the Open Geospatial Consortium. The SSN ontology is based on the Stimulus-Sensor-Observation ontology design pattern. The SSN ontology describes sensors (i.e. *ssn:Sensor*) as physical objects that observe and transform incoming stimuli into another representation, where stimuli (i.e. *ssn:Stimulus*) are changes or states in an environment that a sensor uses to measure a property and where observations (i.e. *ssn:Observation*) are contexts for interpreting incoming stimuli and fixing parameters such as time and location. Since the SSN ontology provides only core concepts, it needs to be extended with domain specific terms. Those specific terms already existing in the Urban Energy model, have been used; while those that are not included in it, have been created as concepts of the OPTIMUS ontology.

Figure 8 shows an excerpt of the OPTIMUS ontology referring to dynamic data, in particular the energy production sensors of the Sant Cugat pilot. It includes a sensor –SunnyPortal– composed of two subsystems –SunnyPortal_EnergyProduction and SunnyPortal_SolarRadiation–that can be located in different places –building, room, and technical system– modelled with specific terms created for the OPTIMUS ontology. The sensors read some properties (i.e. *PVSystem_Peak_Power* and *Solar_Irradiation*) borrowed from the Urban Energy ontology. The outputs of the observations are modelled with OPTIMUS concepts such as *PVSystem_Peak_PowerSensorOutput* and *Solar_IrradiationSensorOutput*.

³ http://wsmls.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/global/DUL-Modules/SpatialRelations/0.1/DUL_SpatialRelations.html

Figure 8. Excerpt of the OPTIMUS ontology for conceptualizing energy production sensors

3.2 Ontology coding

The OPTIMUS ontology has been coded in OWL language using the ClickOn ontology editor⁴ (Figure 9) developed in the SEMANCO project (Wolters, Nemirovski and Nolle, 2013). This editor provides a user-friendly interface which facilitates the ontology building process. The interface of the ClickOn editor is composed of two simultaneous views of an ontology: one to edit the taxonomy of concepts (e.g. family of sensors), and a second one to edit the aggregation relations (e.g. sensor output).

⁴ <http://semanco-tools.eu/click-on>

Figure 9. ClickOn ontology editor used for coding the OPTIMUS ontology

At the time of writing, the OPTIMUS ontology at is composed of 74 terms and 33 relations.

4 The Semantic framework

The Semantic framework developed within the OPTIMUS project is composed of a publish-and-subscribe system and a Semantic Service (Figure 10). The purpose of these tools is to integrate data from different sources and domains.

Figure 10. Semantic Framework components

4.1 Ztreamy server

The chosen publish-and-subscribe system is Ztreamy⁵. It is an open-source platform developed by Universidad Carlos III of Madrid for publishing streams of semantically-annotated data (e.g. readings from sensors) on the Web, built on top of the Tornado Web server. The platform supports events described with RDF. It is scalable through replication with real experiments. Up to 40.000 simultaneous clients can publish events with delivery delays of just a few seconds (Arias et al. 2014).

The Ztreamy server is a Web service which receives data from the publishers through a list of streams previously setup in a configuration file (Figure 11). The publishers, that is the data capturing modules developed in WP2, send the data using HTTP calls. For example, a POST call to publish data through the *santcugat_townhall_pv_power* stream to a Ztreamy server instantiated in port 9000 would be sent with the URL *http://server:9000/santcugat_townhall_pv_power/publish*.

```

1 [global]
2 port=9000
3
4 [streams]
5 stream_EPro1= santcugat_townhall_pv_irradiation
6 stream_EPro2= santcugat_townhall_pv_power
7
8 stream_EPro3= savona_school_pv_irradiation
9 stream_EPro4= savona_school_pv_power
10
11 stream_EPri1= spanish_electricity_energycost
12 stream_EPri2= spanish_gas_energycost
13 stream_EPri3= spanish_biomass_energycost
14 stream_EPri4= spanish_fuel_energycost
15 stream_EPri5= spanish_marketstotals_renewableprod
16 stream_EPri6= spanish_marketstotals_totaldemand
17
18 stream_EPri7= italian_electricity_energycost
19 stream_EPri8= italian_gas_energycost
20 stream_EPri9= italian_biomass_energycost
21 stream_EPri10= italian_fuel_energycost

```

Figure 11. Configuration file of the Ztreamy server

⁵ <http://www.ztreamy.org/>

4.2 Semantic Service

The Semantic Service is a subscriber that receives data from a Ztreamy server. The goal of the Semantic Service is to contextualize the data sent by the data capturing modules. The Semantic Service has been developed in Python. Like the server, the service reads a configuration file which contains the list of streams to be listened and the parameters needed for contextualizing the input triples (Figure 12).

```

1 [global]
2 ztreamy_server = http://arcdev.housing.salle.url.edu:9000/
3 sparq_endpoint_url = http://winarc.housing.salle.url.edu:8080/sparql
4 sparq_endpoint_graph = http://optimus-test
5 ## Energy production streams
6 epro_number_streams = 4
7 ## Energy prices streams
8 epri_number_streams = 10
9 ## Social Media streams
10 sm_number_streams = 2
11 ## Weather forecast streams
12 wf_number_streams = 18
13 ## De-centraliced data streams
14 dcd_number_streams = 14
15 #log_level: 0 no log, 1 only errors, 2 all log
16 log_level = 2
17
18 [prefixes]
19 ssn = <http://purl.oclc.org/NEI/ssnx/ssn#>
20 xsd = <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
21 time = <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
22 semanco = <http://semanco-tools.eu/ontology-releases/eu/semanco/ontology/SEMANCO/SEMANCO.owl#>
23 optimus = <http://optimus-smartcity.eu/ontology-releases/eu/semanco/ontology/optimus.owl#>
24
25
26
27 #####
28 ## SANTI CUGAT - TOWN HALL - PV panels - Irradiation
29 [stream_EProl]
30 stream = santcugat_townhall_pv_irradiation
31 owl_sensingdevice_class = optimus:SunnyPortal_SolarRadiation
32 owl_sensingdevice_uri = sunnyportal_solar_radiation
33 owl_observation_uri = sunnyportal_solar_radiation
34 owl_featureofinterest_uri = solar_irradiation
35 owl_featureofinterest_class = optimus:Solar_IrradiationFeature
36 owl_observedproperty_uri = solar_irradiation
37 owl_observedproperty_class = semanco:Solar_Irradiation
38 owl_sensoroutput_class = optimus:Solar_IrradiationSensorOutput

```

Figure 12. Configuration file of the Semantic Service

The contextualization parameters of the configuration file are used to fill the RDF template used to contextualize the input data (Figure 13).

```

<{uri}/observation/{owl_observation_uri}{id}> ssn:featureOfInterest <{uri}/featureofinterest/{owl_featureofinterest_uri}>.
<{uri}/observation/{owl_observation_uri}{id}> ssn:observedProperty <{uri}/property/{owl_observedproperty_uri}>.
<{uri}/sensoroutput/{owl_observation_uri}{id}> rdf:type optimus:{owl_sensoroutput_class}.

<{uri}/sensingdevice/{owl_sensingdevice_uri}> rdf:type {owl_sensingdevice_class}.
<{uri}/featureofinterest/{owl_featureofinterest_uri}> rdf:type optimus:{owl_featureofinterest_class}.
<{uri}/featureofinterest/{owl_featureofinterest_uri}> ssn:hasProperty <{uri}/property/{owl_observedproperty_uri}>.

```

Figure 13. Template for contextualize RDF triples

5 Conclusions

The Semantic framework presented in this report provides a technological solution to integrate the heterogeneous and diverse data retrieved by the data capturing modules developed in WP2 using semantic technologies.

A semantic integration process has been devised to bring together data sources from different domains (i.e. weather data, building energy systems, social media, energy prices, and energy production data). At the core of the integration process lies the OPTIMUS ontology which conceptualizes the urban and the building domain and a set of RDF templates used by the data capturing modules to model the raw data into RDF triples. Moreover, the Semantic Service, a key component of the Semantic framework, uses the RDF templates to contextualize data following the OPTIMUS ontology.

The communication between the DSS and the modules has been based on Ztreamy, a publish-and-subscribe system.

All of the five modules developed within the WP2 have been connected to the OPTIMUS DSS and tested in real conditions.

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